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STS-Med
Small scale thermal solar
district units for Mediterranean
communities
Ref. I-A/2.3/174

REPORT ON TASK 6.5.2 TECHNICAL AND ECONOMIC FEASIBILITY ASSESSMENT

The Cyprus Institute

OCTOBER 2016
THE CYPRUS INSTITUTE
Nicosia, Cyprus

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1 Plant descriptions

The following passages contain a technical presentation of the various plants

1.1 Italy (ARCA)

1.2 Cyprus (The Cyprus Institute)

1.2.1 Solar collector

The Cypriot case study is located in the outskirts of Nicosia on the campus of the Cyprus Institute. The purpose is to supply heating, cooling and hot domestic water to the Novel Technologies Laboratory (NTL, Figure 1.1a) with the help of a Linear Fresnel Reflector (LFR), a thermal storage unit and an absorption chiller.

Figure 1.1. The Novel Technologies Laboratory (a) and Fresnel on rooftop of the public school (b)

The solar collector of the Cyprus Institute was installed on the roof of a public building separated from NTL by a road (Figure 1.1b). The construction of the NTL was finalized in 2013. The Fresnel collector was implemented in July 2016. The main challenge was its integration on the HVAC of the NTL which was supported by a heat-pump, chillers, air handling units, fan coil units and heat recovery units. The global cooling capacity of the system is much higher than the heating capacity (Table 1.1), aligned with the general needs in this area of the Mediterranean Sea. Summers are long and hot (up to 6 months) and winters are quite mild and dry. Fresnel technology relies on is a single-axis tracking strategy, similar to parabolic trough collectors (PTC). Orientation of the collector (axis of the receiver) is North-South, according to the orientation of the NTL.

Table 1.1. List of the components of the HVAC prior to the installation of the Fresnel collector

Components	Numbers	Main characteristics
Heat pump	1	Cooling (capacity 225 kW) and heating (capacity 235 kW)
Chillers	2	Only cooling (total capacity 470 kW)
Air handling units	6	Cooling (total capacity 515 kW) and heating (total capacity 153 kW)
Fan coil units	4	Cooling (total capacity 208.7 kW) and heating (total capacity 93 kW)
Heat recovery units	8	Electrical consumption : 4.1 kW

The mirrors of the collector are rectangular and slightly curved in order to focus the reflected beams on the receiver. The field on the rooftop of the School is composed by 18 parallel rows.

Table 1.2 makes the inventory of the components of the collector. First, per single row, 16 mirrors are aligned (288 mirrors on the collector). Their aperture area is 0.64m^2 (2,000mm x 320mm). The global aperture area of the field is 184.32m^2 . 72 DC motors ensure the rotation of the mirrors, thus means 4 mirrors per motor. The receiver is composed by 8 absorber tubes in parallel. An outer 125mm diameter vacuum glass encloses a central stainless 70 mm diameter steel pipe. The outer tube is a 3 mm thick Borosilicate glass pipe. The length of each single pipe is 3,900 mm. The average solar transmittance of the vacuum glass tube is 96.4%.

Table 1.2. Technical details of the Fresnel collector

Components		Specifications
Mirrors	Number	288
	Number of rows	18
	Number of mirrors per row	16
	Dimensions of the mirrors (aperture area)	2000 mm x 320 mm
	Global aperture area	184.32 m^2
	Number of motors	72
	Number of mirrors driven per motor	4
Vacuum glass tube	Material	Borosilicate glass
	Outer diameter	$125\text{ mm} \pm 1.5\text{ mm}$
	Thickness	$3\text{ mm} \pm 0.4\text{ mm}$
	Length	$3900\text{ mm} + 3\text{ mm}$
	Average solar transmittance (with antireflection coating)	$96.4\% \pm 0.4\%$
Absorber (stainless steel tube)	Material	Stainless steel
	Outer diameter	$70\text{ mm} \pm 0.35\text{ mm}$
	Thickness	$2\text{ mm} \pm 0.2\text{ mm}$
	Length	$4060\text{ mm} + 3\text{ mm}$
Receiver	Number of tubes in series	8
	Global length receiver	32.48 m

1.2.2 Heat transfer fluid

The heat transfer fluid is the heat transfer medium which collects the heat in the receiver. Then the heat is stored in a small buffer tank of 800L where the heat transfer fluid may expand or be preheated for faster start-up. Also, a 3 way-valve bypasses the heat exchanger and regulates the inlet temperature on the collector. All the more, this valve avoids heating the heat transfer fluid thanks to the pressurized water loop. The nominal outlet temperature is 170°C after the outlet of the receiver. The technical characteristics are detailed in Table 1.3.

Table 1.3 Heat transfer fluid characteristics

Category	Value	Unit
Thermal conductivity	$0.142\text{ (}38^\circ\text{C)} / 0.137\text{ (}260^\circ\text{C)}$	W/(m.K)
Specific heat	$2.135\text{ (}38^\circ\text{C)} / 2.386\text{ (}131^\circ\text{C)} / 2.721\text{ (}232^\circ\text{C)}$	kJ/(kg.K)
Density	$850\text{ (}38^\circ\text{C)} / 793\text{ (}131^\circ\text{C)} / 717\text{ (}232^\circ\text{C)}$	kg/L
Viscosity	$4.8\text{ (}40^\circ\text{C)} / 1.3\text{ (}131^\circ\text{C)} / 0.6\text{ (}232^\circ\text{C)}$	mm^2/s

1.2.3 Thermal storage

A 75 kW capacity heat-exchanger between the heat transfer fluid and water is installed on the roof of the KEPA School. The hot fluid leaving the receiver heats the water. Since the temperatures are higher than 100°C, the loop is pressurized with Nitrogen. A thermal storage is included in the loop and stores 100.46kWh thermal at up to 146°C (up to 9bar of pressure), ensuring 2 hours of autonomy for the system (full power in cooling mode). The system can so up to 2 hours after a sudden cloudy weather or sunset. In winter the thermal storage stands for 4 hours for heating. A 3way-valve is also included between the thermal storage and the heat-exchanger with the heat medium loop. Thus so avoids exchanges of heat from the heat medium to the pressurized water loop. As soon the temperature of the tank of pressurized water is higher than 100°C, the valve permits the circulation of pressurized water into the heat exchanger (Figure 2).

Figure 1.2. Thermal storage pressurized with Nitrogen

1.2.4 Heat medium loop

Heat medium loop serves to 2 different uses: heating in winter and cooling in summer with the support of the absorption chiller. Another smaller buffer tank of water (800 L), with a maximum average temperature of 90°C will smooth the inlet temperature of the single effect absorption chiller. The nominal inlet temperature of the chiller is 88°C and the nominal outlet temperature is 83°C. The coefficient of performance is 0.7 and the cooling capacity is 35 kW. All technical specifications of the heat medium loop are summarised in Table 1.4.

Table 1.4: Heat medium loop

Category	Value	Unit
Thermal storage temperature	90	°C
Thermal storage capacity	800	L
Nominal flow rate in the loop (P3.1 and P3.2)	2.47	L.s ⁻¹
Nominal inlet temperature absorption chiller	88	°C
Nominal inlet temperature absorption chiller	83	°C
Nominal cooling power	35	kW
Coefficient of performance (COP)	0.7	-

1.2.5 General drawing

The loops of oil, the storage and heat medium are detailed in Figure 3. The oil loop initiates with the Fresnel collector and terminates with the heat-exchanger with the thermal storage loop. The heat exchanger is located on the roof where the Fresnel collector stands. The loop crosses the NTL building till the area where the heat-pump and chillers are installed.

Figure 1.3. Schematics of the loops

1.3 Egypt (Elsewedy/ASRT)

1.4 Jordan (Millennium/ALBUN)

The plant is installed on the rooftop of Al-Khawarizmi building shown in the figures below at Al-Husson College University. The geographic location of the plant is:

- Latitude: 32.487 N.
- Longitude: 35.89 E.
- Elevation: 648m.

1.4.1 Description of the plant

The plant generates electric power, cooling/heating, hot water and distilled water from a single source of energy (solar energy). Solar energy is collected and concentrated in parabolic trough collectors. The concentrated solar radiation heats the heat transfer fluid (HTF) which is thermal oil to a temperature of 240°C. The heated oil is stored in a break tank to provide a stabilized operation for the heat consuming equipment.

In summer, the hot thermal oil drives an absorption chiller to provide space cooling through two Fan-Coil units in one of the classrooms. The oil is also utilized to generate superheated steam through saturated steam generator and super-heater. The super-heated steam drives small steam turbo-generator to generate electricity, the turbine is fed with soft water from a water softener. The steam exits the turbine in a liquid phase (condensate) which is collected in a tank and used as distilled water. If the available solar energy exceeds the cooling and electricity generation demands, the excess heat is delivered to hot water network through shell and tube heat exchanger and the hot water will be stored in a hot water tank. If the excess heat exceeds the storage capacity, it will be dissipated in a dry cooler.

In winter, the operation will be similar to summer operation with space cooling replaced by space heating which will be provided by the hot water stored in through the fan-coil units.

The schematic diagram below illustrates the plant components and interconnecting piping as well as plant instrumentation.

Figure 1.4: Plant Schematic Diagram

1.4.2 Plant components & circuits

The major components of the plant are listed in the table below:

Table 1.5: Jordan plant major components

No.	Item	Type	Ref.	Capacity	Qty	Brand/Origin
1	solar collector	parabolic trough	PTC-1	85 kW _{th} ⁽¹⁾	2	Soltigua/Italy
2	chiller	air-cooled absorption	CHLR-1	17.1 kW _{cool} ⁽²⁾	1	Robur/Italy
3	turbo-generator set	steam driven	ST-1	1.2 kW _e	1	Green Turbine / Netherlands
4	steam generator	shell & tube heat exchanger	STG-1	18kg/hr @ 6.0 bar	1	Local
5	steam super-heater	shell & tube heat exchanger	SH-1	18kg/hr @ 6.0 bar and 200°C	1	Local
6	Oil/water heat exchanger	Shell & tube	HEX-1	44 kW	2	GEA / Netherlands
7	fan-coil unit	2-pipe FCU	FCU-1	8.55 kW total 5.8 kW sensible	2	Petra/Jordan
8	dry cooler	horizontal	DC-1	12 kW	1	GEA/UK
9	dry cooler	horizontal	DC-2	43.4 kW	1	GEA/UK
10	thermal oil pump	inline	HOP-1	1.32 l/s, 27.9m	1	KSB/Germany
10	thermal oil pump	inline	HOP-2	1.32 l/s, 27.9m	1	KSB/Germany
11	thermal oil pump	inline	HOP-3	0.76 l/s, 7.2m	1	KSB/Germany
12	water pump	inline	LP-1	0.75 l/s, 10.9m	1	Wilo/Germany
13	water pump	inline	HEXP-1	0.3 l/s, 3.5m	1	Wilo/Germany
14	water pump	inline	CWP-1	0.29 l/s, 4.8m	1	Wilo/Germany
15	water pump	inline	CWP-2	0.53 l/s, 7.2m	1	Wilo/Germany
16	water pump	vertical multistage	STGP-1	0.2 l/s, 65.4m	1	Wilo/Germany
17	water pump	vertical multistage	RWP-1	0.4 l/s, 30.6m	1	Wilo/Germany
18	hot water tank	cylindrical, steel	HWT-1	1500 liters	1	Lapesa / Spain
19	thermal oil tank	cylindrical, steel	TOT-1	1300 liters	1	Local

(1) 900 W/m DNI, 30°C OUTDOOR AIR TEMPERATURE.

(2) 35°C OUTDOOR AIR TEMPERATURE, SUPPLY WATER TEMPERATURE 7.7°C.

Table 1.6: Solar Field Circuit

Circuit Components	Circuit Function
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Parabolic trough collectors. - Oil circulation pump (HOP-1) - Thermal oil tank (TOT-1) - Piping. - Instrumentation & controls. 	<p>The collectors track the sun and collect solar energy to heat the thermal oil to 240°C. HOP-1 circulates the hot oil between the collectors and TOT-1 where oil is stored at a temperature 220-240°C.</p>

Table 1.7: Chilled Water Circuit

Circuit Components	Circuit Function
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Absorption chiller (CH-1). - Oil circulation pump (HOP-3) - Water circulation pump (LP-1) - Fan coil units (FCUs). - Piping. - Instrumentation & controls. 	<p>This circuit is operational during summer only. HOP-1 circulates the hot oil between TOT-1 and the CH-1 to provide the required heat to drive the absorption cycle. The chiller generates chilled water at 7.7°C. Chilled water will be conveyed through LP-1 to the FCUs to provide space cooling.</p>

Figure 1.5: Jordan Solar Field Circuit

Figure 1.6: Jordan chilled water circuit

Table 1.8: Hot Water & Space Heating Circuit

Circuit Components	Circuit Function
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Oil/water heat exchanger. - Oil circulation pump (HOP-2) - Water circulation pump (HEXP-1). - Hot water tank (HWT-1). - Dry cooler (DC-2). - Circulation pump (CWP-2). - Water circulation pump (LP-1). - Fan coil units (FCUs). - Piping. - Instrumentation & controls. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - HOP-2 circulates the hot oil between TOT-1 and HEX-1 to generate hot water on the other side. The hot water will be circulated between HEX1 and the tank HWT-1 to charge the tank with hot water at up to 90°C. - If there is excess energy in the solar energy and the hot water circuit needs to be kept in operation for demonstration, the excess energy is dissipated in the dry cooler by circulating the hot water between HWT-1 and DC-1 via the pump CWP-2. - In winter only, the hot water in HWT-1 is supplied to the FCUs through LP-1 to provide space heating.

Figure 1.7: Jordan Hot Water Circuit

Table 1.9: Steam Generation Circuit

Circuit Components	Circuit Function
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Steam Generator (STG-1). - Steam Super heater (SH-1) - Oil circulation pump (HOP-2) - Softener (SOF-1). - Raw water pump (RWP-1). - Soft water tank (SWT-1) - Steam generator feed pump (STGP-1) - Piping. - Instrumentation & controls. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - HOP-2 circulates the hot oil between TOT-1 and STG-1 & SH-1. Saturated steam at 4.2barg is generated in STG-1 and superheated in SH-1 up to 200°C. - RWP-1 will deliver raw water from existing roof tanks through SOF-1 to the soft water tank. The water hardness is reduced down to 50 ppm in this process to protect the steam generator against scaling. - The water is fed into the steam generator via STGP-1.

Figure 1.8: Steam Generation Circuit

Table 1.10: Turbo-Generator Circuit

Circuit Components	Circuit Function
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Turbo-generator set. - Steam condenser. - Vacuum pump. - Water circulation pump (CWP-1) - Dry Cooler (DC-1) - Softener (SOF-1). - DC-AC Inverter. - Piping. - Instrumentation & controls. 	<p>This cycle is operated manually and for demonstration only as the system is not connected to the university network.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The super-heated is fed to steam turbine which rotates at maximum speed of 30,000 RPM. - The steam exits the turbine and is condensed in the condenser which is cooled by water circulated between the condenser and DC-1 via CWP-1. - The condensed steam is then transferred through the vacuum pump to the distilled water tank where it is collected and used by the university. - The turbo-generator set generates DC electric power. The DC is converted to AC power in the inverter which is connected to the load

Figure 1.9: Turbo-Generator Circuit

Table 1.11: Controls

Circuit Components	Circuit Function
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Solar field controller (QG). - Solar collector controller (QMB). - Plant control panel (CP-1). - Motor control center (MCC-1) - Steam turbine panel (STP-1) - FCU thermostat controller (TH-) - Instrumentation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - QG controls the operation of the solar field. it sends on/off commands to HOP-1 and QBMs and displays the solar field operational parameters (i.e. temperature, flow rate ... etc) - QBM controls the tracing of the collector and send sensors reading to QG. - CP-1 controls the other components in the plant that are operated automatically. - MCC-1 provides power and motor controls for the all system components. - STP-1 provides the operator with switches to manually operate the turbo-generator circuit. - TH- controls the operation of the FCU and its control valve according to room temperature.

2 Simulation results and financial analysis

The following passages describe the technical performance and the financial environment, as well as a few possible economic performance metrics for all four systems in the respective countries of installation.

2.1 Italy (ARCA)

2.2 Cyprus (The Cyprus Institute)

Simulations were performed under Simulation Studio of TRNSYS and METEONORN data. All the loops were integrated up to the absorption chiller and heat recovery in winter (Figure 4). In the model, the absorption chiller is not connected the HVAC of the NTL. The chiller is ON when the outdoor temperature is higher than 27°C and the heat-recovery is ON when the same temperature is lower than 18°C (based on TMY). The Direct Normal Irradiance (DNI) may reach 933W.m⁻² in summer and 500W.m⁻² in winter (Figure 5). Based on a Typical Meteorological Year, the peak power summer reaches 71.21 kW. But in December and January the daily peak productions are below 15kW. The annual power output of the Fresnel collector is illustrated in Figure 6.

Figure 2.1. TRNSYS Model of the Cypriot platform

Figure 2.2. Meteonorm Data (DNI)

Figure 2.3. Simulated power output of the Fresnel collector

The objective of the platform is to provide chilled water at 7°C in summer and hot water at 55°C in winter. The simulation results are exposed in Figure 7.

Figure 2.4. Chilled water and hot water temperatures

2.2.1 Operational data

This section exposes the temperature of the tank of oil, of pressurized water and heat medium base don the experiment of the 29th of Spetember 2016. Figure 8 reports the evolution of the temperature of the oil from 9.00 AM to 8.00 PM. The temperature in the morning was around 70°C and was heated up to 165°C after noon. The Thermostat function then was charging the thermal storage through cycles.

Figure 2.5. Temperature of the buffer of oil

Each time the heat from the thermal oil loop was released the thermal storage temperature was increasing as shown in Figure 9. From 105°C around noon, the storage was charged thermally till 146°C along the afternoon. Around 4.30 PM the heat was released to the heat medium loop as shown in Figure 10. Before 5.00 PM the absorption chiller was activated and the heat medium temperature decreased from 95°C to 78°C.

Figure 2.6. Thermal storage temperature

Figure 2.7. Heat medium storage

2.2.2 Plant cost breakdown

The following table is an analytical breakdown of the upfront costs of the plant.

Table 2.1: Cyprus plant cost breakdown

Item	€	€/kWth
solar collectors, foundations & tracking system	€90,000	€1,264
Absorption chiller	€51,410	€722
Electricity generation (steam, PV, ORC etc.)	€22,378	€314
Storage tanks & pressure vessels	€4,214	€59
thermal oil	€10,960	€154
piping network, valves, heat exchangers, pumps	€44,050	€619
Control, electrical and IT equipment	€18,862	€265
installation and commissioning	€27,645	€388
Other (coolers, FCUs, water descalers, security)	€8,031	€113
Meteorological equipment	€13,984	€196
Total	€291,534	€4,094

2.2.3 Investment Indicators in Cyprus

The inflation rate in Cyprus has been fluctuating between 1% and 5% since 2006, with deflation seen regularly since 2014. It is assumed here that the annual average inflation rate will be around the 1.5% mark for the foreseeable future, in line with the Cyprus' central bank targets.

The discount rate for such an investment decision is also set at 7% nominal rate, or at 4.39% real rate, adjusted for the inflation rate mentioned. There is no steadfast way to determine this with certainty since it depends, among others, on the state of the economy, the willingness of credit institutions to support such infrastructures, etc. It is however a figure usual in such projects with a minimum amount of risk. There are also no assumptions on insurance costs, taxation of revenues and/or profits, or any costs associated with debt financing; it's assumed that it's all financed through equity. Most of these assumptions (apart from the inflation rate) apply to all the systems examined in this report.

2.2.4 Financial metrics of plant in Cyprus

The feed in tariff in Cyprus for solar thermal systems has been abolished in 2013, but a net-metering scheme for feeding electricity in the network has replaced it. Currently the electricity retail rate is around 0.18€/kWh, relevant to the housing and commercial sector. This however fails to capture the nature of polygenerative plants that produce commodities other than electricity only. The Cypriot plant is configured to provide cooling and heating to indoor spaces and produce electricity via PV cells embedded in the structure. This is reflected in the following table:

Table 2.2: Energy and monetary conversion for the plant in Jordan¹

Subsystem	Output / year	Annual benefit / year
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¹ Source: Kiwan, S., Damseh, R., Venezia, L., Montagnino, F.M., Paredes, F., 2016. Techno-Economic Performance Analysis of a Concentrated Solar Polygeneration Plant in Jordan. Presented at the GCREEDER 2016, Amman, Jordan.

Cooling (est.)	10,000 kWh _{th}	€1,800
Heating (est.)	12,000 kWh _{th}	€2,160
Electricity (est.)	15,000 kWh _{elec}	€2,700
Total		€6,660

In the case of water, the conversion rate of m³ produced to monetary value is taken from the same source at 0.0816 €/m³. This is an overall ‘benefit’ of €2,832 for one year.

The above assumptions result in a set of financial indicators as shown below:

Non-discounted payback time: **58.9yrs**
NPV of investment: **-€241k**
LCOE: **0.88 €/kWh**

These number do not compare favourably with contemporary renewable energy solutions in the commercial sphere. One however should bear in mind that the plant in Cyprus is a pilot system used to showcase various ways of producing commodities using a singular source of energy, and bringing relevant stakeholders in contact with the technology. The aims of the project were never to produce a system with commercial aspirations. If indeed this was the vision, polygeneration would be pared down and focus would be given in the most revenue-rich modality (in this case space heating), more off-the shelf components would be used and more conventional decisions would be taken.

2.3 [Egypt \(Elsewedy/ASRT\)](#)

2.4 [Jordan \(Millennium/ALBUN\)](#)

2.4.1 Plant simulation results

The following graphs illustrate the system simulation results for the plant operation:

Figure 2.8: Direct Normal Irradiance (W/m²) in the plant site

Figure 2.9: Solar field output temperature (°C)

Figure 2.10: Annual space heating

Figure 2.11: Annual space cooling

Figure 2.12: Annual steam turbine output

Figure 2.13: Annual distilled water production

2.4.2 Plant operation results

The following graphs illustrate the actual output of the plant for the early days of operation in October 2016 for the solar field and the absorption chiller.

Figure 2.14: Daily direct Solar Irradiance (13-Oct-2016)

Figure 2.15: Solar Field Performance (13-Oct-2016)

Figure 2.16: Solar field temperatures (13-Oct-2016)

Figure 2.17: Daily direct Solar Irradiance (14-Oct-2016)

Figure 2.18: Solar Field Performance (14-Oct-2016)

Figure 2.19: Solar field temperatures (14-Oct-2016)

Figure 2.20: Daily direct Solar Irradiance (15-Oct-2016)

Figure 2.21: Solar Field Performance (15-Oct-2016)

Figure 2.22: Solar field temperatures (15-Oct-2016)

Figure 2.23: Absorption chiller performance (16-Oct-2016)

2.4.3 Plant cost breakdown

The following table is an analytical breakdown of the upfront costs of the plant.

Table 2.3: Jordan plant cost breakdown

No.	item	cost (Euro)	No.	item	cost (Euro)
1	solar collectors with tracking system, instrumentation and control	€130,943	10	dry coolers	€8,575
2	steel structure for collectors	€16,912	11	Fan-Coil units	€4,378
3	Absorption chiller	€31,140	12	water softening system	€1,555
4	steam generator	€20,302	13	expansion and pressure vessels	€3,623
5	steam turbine & its accessories	€11,858	14	Equipment foundations	€2,811
6	thermal oil pumps	€10,861	15	thermal oil	€7,805
7	steam/water heat exchanger	€4,380	16	control and instrumentation	€39,661
8	hot water storage tank (1500 liter)	€4,700	17	pipng network with insulation and cladding, valves, etc.	€44,204
8	thermal oil storage tank (1300 liter)	€5,726	18	power and control cables and raceways and electric panels	€7,104
9	water pumps	€4,927	19	installation and commissioning	€42,990
				total	€404,455

2.4.4 Investment Indicators in Jordan

The inflation rate in Jordan has been fluctuating considerably in the last 15 years, from deflation (in 2009 and 2015) to 13.8% in 2008. Analysts such as the IMF and the World Bank seem to agree that the annual average inflation rate will be hovering around the 2.5% for the foreseeable future.

Data on discount rates, taxation debt costs etc. are the same as in all other cases in this report.

2.4.5 Financial metrics of plant in Jordan

The feed in tariff in Jordan is 0.12/kWh for solar systems on net metering basis, relevant to the housing sector. For CSP systems however the tariff for electricity generation in place at the moment is USD 0.183/kWh, or €0.168²/kWh. This however fails to capture the nature of polygenerative plants that produce commodities other than electricity only. The Jordanian plant is configured to provide cooling and heating to indoor spaces and produce distilled water, in addition to electricity production, as seen in the technical presentation sections above. This is reflected in the following table:

Table 2.4: Energy and monetary conversion for the plant in Jordan³

Subsystem	Output / year	Annual benefit / year
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² Exchange rate at 1 USD = 0.91671 EUR on 28/10/16

³ Source: Kiwan, S., Damseh, R., Venezia, L., Montagnino, F.M., Paredes, F., 2016. Techno-Economic Performance Analysis of a Concentrated Solar Polygeneration Plant in Jordan. Presented at the GCREEDER 2016, Amman, Jordan.

Cooling	2,618 kWh _{th}	€440
Heating	12,240 kWh _{th}	€2,056
Distilled Water	360 m ³	€29.4
Electricity	1,825 kWh _{elec}	€307
Total		€2,832

In the case of water, the conversion rate of m³ produced to monetary value is taken from the same source at 0.0816 €/m³. This is an overall ‘benefit’ of €2,832 for one year.

The above assumptions result in a set of financial indicators as shown below:

Non-discounted payback time: **277yrs**
NPV of investment: **-€388k**
LCOE: **2.56 €/kWh**

These number do not compare favourably with contemporary renewable energy solutions in the commercial sphere. One however should bear in mind that the plant in Jordan is a pilot system used to showcase various ways of producing commodities using a singular source of energy, and bringing relevant stakeholders in contact with the technology. The aims of the project were never to produce a system with commercial aspirations. If indeed this was the vision, polygeneration would be pared down and focus would be given in the most revenue-rich modality (in this case space heating), more off-the shelf components would be used and more conventional decisions would be taken.

2.5 Overall upfront cost comparison

The following chart shows a comparison among the upfront costs associated with the different plants. Variations can be explained by different system design and configuration, different market conditions, different sizes and differences in costs that are associated with procurement, integration and commissioning, each varying from country to country.

